

Studies on Azido Complexes of Cobalt—Part 2

S. K. CHATTERJEE and S. K. BOSE

Department of Pure Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-700 009, India

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The effects of solvents (water, DMSO, glycerol-water) on the u.v. absorption spectra of a few azido complexes of Co(III) have been studied. It has been observed that the absorption peaks are dependent on the composition of the solvent medium.

THE effect of solvents on charge transfer spectra of metal complexes, apart from their own intrinsic interest, have received attention as they throw light on the photochemically active precursors upon irradiation in the charge transfer region.

While a lot of data is available for acidopentamine complexes of the type $\text{Co(III)L}_5\text{X}^-$, complexes of the type $\text{Co(III)L}_4(\text{X}^-)_2$ and $\text{Co(III)L}_3(\text{X}^-)_3$, which are capable of forming *cis* and *trans* isomers, have received little attention. The object of the present investigation is to study the effects of the medium (water, glycerol solution and dimethyl sulphoxide) on the charge transfer spectra of *cis* and *trans* azido complexes of Co(III).

Experimental

The compounds have been prepared by standard methods and their spectra recorded in Beckman spectrophotometer Model DU. The blank in each case consists of a solution having the same medium composition as that of the complex solution. The spectra of *cis* and *trans* $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{N}_3$ were taken in an NaOAc/HOAc and phthalate buffer solution of pH 4 respectively in order to prevent hydrolysis. Except for slight changes in the value of the molar absorbance, peak positions in the visible and u.v. regions, remain unaltered in the pH range 3-5. Since $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$ is sparingly soluble in DMSO and $[\text{Co}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{ClO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is sparingly soluble in water, absorption maxima for these two compounds were obtained by plotting absorbance of nearly saturated solutions of these compounds in DMSO and water respectively.

There is some controversy about *cis* $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{N}_3)]$. The method of preparation¹ for both *cis* and *trans* triazido complex is by warming aqueous solutions of either *cis* or *trans* $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{N}_3$ with sodium azide and ammonium sulphate at 60° with subsequent cooling of the reaction mixture. It was pointed out later² that *trans* $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{N}_3)]$ is the exclusive product, whether one starts with *cis* or *trans* bisazido complex. It has been observed, however, that on cooling the reaction

mixture containing the *cis* bisazido complex, various fractions of crystals are obtained. The last crop of crystals, obtained on prolonged cooling of the mother liquor in ice, on analysis, conforms to a triazido complex, with the following absorption bands in DMSO: visible, (550 n.m., 18180 cm^{-1} , $\epsilon_M=212$) and u.v., (315 n.m., 31750 cm^{-1} , $\epsilon_M=20850$). For the *trans* compound literature data³ for the visible band in DMSO is 16990 cm^{-1} . Like the *trans* triazido complex, it is also insoluble in water and dissolves only in DMSO.

Results and Discussion

For all compounds a blue shift is observed in going from a solvent of lower dielectric constant, DMSO to one with a higher dielectric constant, water. A specific interaction between solute and solvent causes the shifts and the shifts are not related to the overall dielectric constant of the medium.

From peak position of the CTTM (charge transfer to metal) bands as given in Table 1, shifts as small as 340 cm^{-1} , as is observed for $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3]\text{Cl}_2$, may appear to be trivially small but it is clear from Fig. 1, (absorption spectra of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3]\text{Cl}_2$ in different solvents) that the band in DMSO as a whole undergoes a distinct red shift with respect to water.

For *cis* and *trans* bisazido pairs, the blue shift is more pronounced for the *cis* than for the *trans* (Figs. 2 and 3).

In conventional charge transfer complexes of the donor acceptor type a red shift of the charge transfer band is observed with increasing dielectric constant of the medium⁴. This is attributed to a progressively greater stabilisation of the excited state with the increasing polarity of the solvent medium.

In contrast to this behaviour, for all the complexes studied here, a blue shift is observed with increase in solvent polarity. This behaviour is in

TABLE I

Complex	$\lambda_{\max}(\text{nm})$,	$\nu_{\max}(\text{cm}^{-1})$	$\Delta\nu_{\max}^*(\text{cm}^{-1})$	Solvent Conditions
$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3]\text{Cl}_2$	308,	38000	210	Water DMSO
	305,	32790		
<i>cis</i> $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{N}_3$	308,	32470	110	NaOAc/HOAc buffer pH 4 90% glycerol in buffer
	309,	32360		
	317,	31550	920	DMSO
<i>trans</i> $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{N}_3$	340,	29410	80	Phthalate buffer pH 4 90% glycerol in buffer
	341,	29880		
	346,	28900	510	DMSO
<i>cis</i> $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_3(\text{N}_3)_3]$	306,	32680	990	DMSO + H ₂ O (10% DMSO) (a) DMSO & (b) DMSO + Dioxane (1 : 1)
	315,	31750		
<i>cis</i> $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{ClO}_4$	305,	32790	580	(a) water & (b) 72% glycerol 90% glycerol DMSO
	307,	32570		
	310,	32260		
<i>trans</i> $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{ClO}_4$	340,	29410	340	Water (a) 50% glycerol & (b) 90% glycerol DMSO
	341,	29830		
	344,	29070		
<i>trans</i> $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{N}_3\text{Cl}]\text{ClO}_4$	321,	31150	1080	(a) water (b) 50% glycerol (c) 90% glycerol (d) 50% (by wt.) of sucrose DMSO
	332,	30120		
<i>trans</i> $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})_2(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{ClO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	302,	38110	210	Water DMSO
	307,	32570		

* Red shift with respect to water.

Absorption spectra of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{N}_3)]\text{Cl}_2$
in various media: DMSO (—),
90% glycerol (---),
water (— · — · —)

Fig. 1

Absorption spectra of *Cis* $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4$
 $(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{N}_3$ in various media: DMSO (—),
90% glycerol (---), Sodiumacetate-
acetic acid buffer, pH-4, (— · — · —).
water (· · · · ·)

Fig. 2

Absorption spectra of *trans* $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{N}_3$ in various media: DMSO (—), 90% glycerol (----), Potassium hydrogen phthalate buffer, pH-4 (— · —).

Fig. 3

conformity with the known behaviour⁴ of compounds with an asymmetry in charge distribution and in which the transfer of charge is from ligand to metal (CTTM). During this transfer of charge the dipole moment of the excited state is reduced. The ground state, due to its higher dipole moment, is stabilised to a greater extent than the excited state.

Trans $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{N}_3\text{Cl}]\text{ClO}_4$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3]\text{Cl}_2$ belong to point group C_{4v} . Both *cis* bisazido and *trans* triazido complexes belong to C_{2v} . The symmetry of *cis* triazido² is C_{3v} , while that of *trans* bisazido is D_{4h} . Hence the above explanation cannot be used for the *trans* bisazido complexes, which cannot have a dipole moment due to the presence of a centre of inversion. It should be remarked that the azide ion is a linear polyatomic molecule, and if present in an eclipsed conformation, about the tetragonal axis, can bring about slight asymmetry in charge distribution in *trans* bisazido complexes.

Absorption maxima of all these compounds, in solutions with a low concentration of glycerol (50-70% by volume) and solutions containing 50% by weight of cane sugar, correspond to that in water. Even by using highly concentrated glycerol solution (90% by volume), there is little or no change in spectral peaks with respect to water. But a distinct

red shift is observed in DMSO with respect to water although the dielectric constant of a 90% by volume aqueous solution of glycerol⁵ and that of DMSO⁶ are nearly equal (≈ 46). It is clear that dielectric constant, a bulk property of the medium, is not responsible for the shift. This is further corroborated by the observation that in mixed solvents such as DMSO+water & DMSO+dioxane, containing varying amounts of DMSO and dioxane, the peak positions do not undergo any intermediate shifts, but correspond entirely to that of the more polar solvent.

In both aqueous and non-aqueous media, the complex is exclusively in a solvent cage of the more polar component and remains unaffected by an increase in concentration of the less polar component.

In a few cases (*cis* and *trans* bisazido pairs), very high concentrations of glycerol is able to effect, although to a very small extent, the solvent cage of water molecules, and hence small shifts in peak positions are observed.

$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3]\text{Cl}_2$ is the only exception since a red shift of 550 cm^{-1} , with respect to ν_{max} in water, has been observed⁴ in 90% glycerol. This is significantly greater than the observed red shift 210 cm^{-1} in DMSO. As the dielectric constant of the two media are nearly equal, it is probable, that some sort of specific interaction is occurring involving a charge transfer from solvent⁴ to Co(III), as both glycerol and DMSO are more easily oxidisable than water.

A possible explanation for the exceptional behaviour of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3]\text{Cl}_2$ may be due to its high cationic charge, being the largest amongst the series of compounds studied. For highly charged cations the scope of solute solvent interactions is widened to include medium components of lower polarity (glycerol). For lower cationic charge, propensity for interaction with components of lower polarity in a mixed solvent medium, is less or at least small enough to have no effect on the spectra.

A correlation is observed between CTTM bands and the ligand band when the complex does not contain any highly electronegative and/or strongly back bonding ligand (Fig. 4).

A linear relationship is found to exist between the wave number of charge transfer bands and those of the first band (Table 2). Similar relationships were also found⁷ for singlet and triplet transitions for complexes of cobalt(III). This implies that the bands originate from and terminate at orbitals which are similar in nature. For ligands like azido, which have an extra lone pair of electrons available⁸, after forming σ bonds with the metal, the charge transfer band is of type $e_g \leftarrow \pi$, i.e., from a π

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	Compound	1st Band	3rd Band	Solvent	Reference
1.	$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3]\text{Cl}_2$	19280	33000	Water Water	This work 14
2.	$\text{cis}[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{N}_3$	18520	32470	NaOAc/HOAc buffer of pH 4	This work
2A.	$\text{cis}[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{ClO}_4$	18580		Water	7
3.	$\text{trans}[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{N}_3$	17610	29410	Phthalate buffer pH 4 Water	This work 7
4.	$\text{cis}[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_3(\text{N}_3)_3]$	18180	32680	$\text{DMSO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	This work
5.	$\text{trans}[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_3(\text{N}_3)_3]$	17060	29330	$\text{DMSO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	This work
6.	$\text{cis}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{ClO}_4$	16900 19080	32790	DMSO Water & buffer of pH 4 Water	2 This work 8
7.	$\text{trans}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{ClO}_4$	17610 17650	29410 29500	Water & buffer of pH 4 Water	This work 8
8.	$\text{trans}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{N}_3\text{Cl}]\text{ClO}_4$	17300 17310	31150 31250	Water & buffer of pH 4 Water	This work 8
9.	$\text{trans}[\text{Co}(\text{Dipy})_2(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{ClO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	19460	33110	Water	This work
9A.	$\text{trans}[\text{Co}(\text{Dipy})_2(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{N}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	19400		Water	12
10.	$\text{cis}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{N}_3\text{SCN}]\text{S}_2\text{O}_6$	19690	33780	Water	11
11.	$\text{trans}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{N}_3\text{SCN}]\text{ClO}_4$	18740	32680	Water	11
12.	$\text{cis}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{NH}_3\text{N}_3]\text{S}_2\text{O}_6$	19180	33110	Water	11
13.	$\text{cis}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{N}_3^-\text{Cl}]\text{ClO}_4^+$	19100	32200	Water	8

Plot of C.T. Band vs. First Band

- data from literature,
- data from this work.

Fig. 4

molecular orbital localised at the ligand to the anti-bonding e_g orbitals of the metal^{9,10}. Progressive substitution by more azido groups do not affect the overall symmetry of the complex as the ligand bands do not undergo any splitting.

In complexes such as *cis* and *trans* $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{N}_3\text{NO}_2]\text{ClO}_4$ where bands other than the first and third occur¹¹ this linear relationship does not hold. This is also true for bisazido *o*-phenanthroline complex¹². Since the third and first band of bisazido bipyridyl complex¹², falls on this line, it is quite probable that the assignment of these bands in this complex is similar to the other azido complexes of cobalt(III). Such a correlation is not found for the u.v. and visible bands of *cis* and *trans* $[\text{Co}(\text{big H})_2(\text{N}_3)_2]\text{N}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, the synthesis and spectral characteristics of which were reported¹³ in part I.

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